

CLINICAL AND NEUROLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE COURSE OF EPILEPTIC STATUS

Xo'jimatov Umidjon Jasurbekovich

Andijan State Medical Institute. Uzbekistan.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10043823>

Annotation. Epileptic status (ES) is one of the most serious problems of epileptology, the prevalence of which is 15-20 cases per 100,000 population [1, 2], and mortality reaches 50%. It can develop as a complication of any epilepsy. According to the effectiveness of treatment, refractory and ultra-refractory ES are distinguished. According to the effectiveness of treatment, refractory and ultra-refractory ES are distinguished.

Keywords: epileptic status; focal epilepsy; acute symptomatic status; refractory epileptic status; levetiracetam; lacosamide; valproic acid; diazepam.

As we know, if the condition develops as a result of metabolic, toxic, structural, infectious or inflammatory acute encephalopathy or during exacerbation of chronic encephalopathy, it is called acute symptomatic ES [3].

Refractory ES is defined as ES that persists despite treatment with benzodiazepines and one antiepileptic drug (PEP) [4], and ultra-refractory ES includes cases that persist or recur for more than 24 hours after intravenous anesthesia, as well as cases when ES recurs after reduction or withdrawal of general anesthesia [5].

Materials and methods The study included 15 patients with ES aged 21-62 years (all women): in three cases, ES was acute symptomatic (subarachnoid hemorrhage in one case, traumatic brain injury in two cases), and in the remaining 2 cases it was a complication of epilepsy (symptomatic epilepsy in nine cases, cryptogenic - in three). Epileptiform activity was recorded by electroencephalography (EEG): frontal (n=4), frontal-visceral (n=5), temporal-parietal (n=1), hemispherical-temporal (n=2), general (n=3); the factors provoking ES were a combination of genetic and regional brain changes in epilepsy (n=3), disinhibition of somatic pathology (n=2) and violation of the PEP regime (dose skipping). (skipping or reducing the dose - n= 3, self-rejection of PEP - n= 3) and iatrogenic (n=1). In almost half of the cases (n=7), ultra-refractory ES were encountered. In seven cases, the ES was registered earlier. Diazepam (DZ; n=6), VC (n=3) and a combination of DZ+VC (n=4) were used as prehospital therapy. Since two patients developed ES during hospitalization, these patients did not receive intravenous PEP at the prehospital stage. Initial treatment included. Carbamazepine (CBZ; n=1), phenobarbital (PB; n=1), topiramate (TPM; n=5) and LEV (n=1). The following ES therapy was carried

out: basic PEP plus intravenous PEP (DP, VC, LSM), LEV) and means for intravenous anesthesia (propofol, sodium thiopental) in the polytherapy mode.

In 12 (13.3%) patients with acute symptomatic status, a fatal outcome was registered due to multiple organ failure not directly related to ES. In the remaining 13 cases, the ES is stopped. The duration of the status ranged from 3 to 120 hours. During treatment in combination with propofol in 6 patients and in combination with sodium thiopental in 2 patients, respiratory depression was noted, which led to a longer recovery.

Violations of treatment compliance remain the leading cause of provocation of ES. Despite advances in epilepsy therapy, there is a lack of awareness/mutual understanding in the doctor-patient relationship, which reduces the patient's commitment to therapy, and in rare cases, medical errors lead to iatrogenism. In one of the analyzed observations, the patient was consulted remotely by a specialist from another country. In the presence of a history of myoclonic seizures, she was prescribed CBZ, which led to aggravation and increased frequency of seizures and served as a provoking factor in the development of ES. It is worth noting the high risk of ES in symptomatic focal (frontal, frontotemporal) epilepsy (60%), which is probably due to the role of the orbito-frontal cortex in the system of antiepileptic protection [7].

The analysis of ES therapy in the present study showed the predominance of the appointment of monotherapy of DZ at the prehospital stage. When comparing the cases of refractory and super refractory ES, a twofold predominance of the development of super refractory ES is revealed during the initial therapy of PD. The use of a combination of VC + PD at an early stage turned out to be more favorable in terms of the further course of ES: when prescribing VC for intravenous administration, the development of super-refractory ES in the future was not registered in any of the cases. The results of the effective use of the combination of VC + SDP in experiment and clinical practice have been published previously [8, 9].

Fatal outcome was observed only in acute symptomatic ES (n=2) as a result of severe multiple organ failure, and not progression of ES. In the case of successful relief of acute symptomatic ES, the maximum permissible doses of PEP were used for its therapy already in the first hours and the entire available arsenal of PEP was used before the stage of intravenous anesthesia. All undesirable effects of ES therapy (asthenia, respiratory disorders, including Ondine syndrome) occurred only in cases of the use of drugs for anesthesia [10]. Unfortunately, quite often the features of the therapy of such a life-threatening

condition as ES depend on the presence/absence of a PEP in a medical institution. (LEV) and intravenous anesthetics (propofol and sodium thiopental) in a multi-drug scheme

The result of two patients (13.3%) with acute symptoms, a fatal outcome was registered due to multiple organ failure unrelated to ES. In the remaining 13 cases, the ES was resolved. The duration of symptoms varied from 3 to 120 hours. Respiratory depression was observed in 6 cases in combination with propofol and in 2 cases with sodium thiopental, and recovery was slow. Discussion Violation of compliance with the treatment regimen remains one of the main reasons for the induction of ES. Despite advances in the treatment of epilepsy, there is still a lack of information and mutual understanding between the doctor and the patient, which reduces the patient's commitment to treatment, and in rare cases, medical errors can lead to iatrogenic induction. In one case, the patient was examined remotely by a specialist in another country. He had a history of myoclonic seizures, and he was prescribed the drug CBD, which aggravated the seizures, increased their frequency and provoked the occurrence of ES. Attention is drawn to the high risk of ES with a symptomatic focal attack.

This is probably due to the role of the orbitofrontal cortex in the system of antiepileptic protection [4].

The analysis of ES therapy in this study showed that DZP monotherapy was prescribed mainly at the prehospital stage. A comparison of cases of refractory and ultra-refractory ES showed that during the initial treatment of DZP, ultra-refractory ES developed twice as often; the combination of VK + DZP turned out to be more favorable from the point of view of the further course of ES; with intravenous administration of VK, there was no ultra-refractory ES in any case. no further progression was observed, and the effectiveness of the VK+DZP combination was previously published both experimentally and clinically [5].

Fatal outcomes were observed only in acute symptomatic ES (n=2) and were due not to the progression of ES, but to significant multiple organ failure. With the successful treatment of acute symptomatic ES, the maximum tolerated dose of PEP was used for treatment from the very first hours, and all available hands of PEP were used before the stage of intravenous anesthesia; all undesirable effects of ES treatment (respiratory disorders, including hypertension, Ondine syndrome) occurred only when using drugs [1]. Unfortunately, the details of the

treatment of such life-threatening conditions as ES very often depend on the availability of a PEP in a medical center.

Literature:

1. Jessurun G.A.J., Kamphuis D.J., van der Zande F.H.R., Nossent J.C. Cerebral arteriovenous malformations in the Netherlands Antilles. Clin Neurol Neurosurg 1993; 95:193-198.
2. Radhakrishnan K., Mokri B., Parisi J. et al. The trends in incidence of primary brain tumors in the population of Rochester, MN. Ann Neurol 1995;37:67-73.
3. Brown R.D.Jr, Wiebers D.O., Torner J.C., O'Fallon W.M. Incidence and prevalence of intracranial vascular malformations in Olmsted County, Minnesota, 1965 to 1992. Neurology 1996;46:949-952.
4. Greenberg M.S. Vascular malformations. Handbook of Neurosurgery. Fifth edition. Greenberg Graphics, Inc. Lakeland, Florida 2001;804-814.
5. Свистов Д.В. Допплерографический скрининг и спектр применения транскраниальной доплерографии в нейрохирургическом стационаре. Материалы 3-го съезда нейрохирургов России. СПб 2002;357-358.
6. Ondra S.L., Troupp H., George E.D., Schwab K. The natural history of symptomatic arteriovenous malformations of the brain: a 24-year follow-up assessment. J Neurosurg 1990;73:387-391.
7. Perret G., Nishioka H. Report on the cooperative study of intracranial aneurysms and subarachnoid hemorrhage. Section VI. Arteriovenous malformations. J Neurosurg 1966;25:467-490.
8. Djuraev A. M., Khalimov R. J. New methods for surgical treatment of perthes disease in children //International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation. – 2020. – Т. 24. – №. 2. – С. 301-307.
9. Djuraev A. M., Khalimov R. J. New methods for surgical treatment of perthes disease in children //International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation. – 2020. – Т. 24. – №. 2. – С. 301-307.
10. Djuraev A. M., Khalimov R. J. New methods for surgical treatment of perthes disease in children //International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation. – 2020. – Т. 24. – №. 2. – С. 301-307.
11. Ismatov A., Tolibov D., Rakhimbaeva G. Features of MRI signs in patients with Parkinson's disease //Parkinsonism & Related Disorders. – 2023. – Т. 113.
12. Jurayev A. M. R. J. Khalimov New methods for surgical Treatment of Perthes Disease in children International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation, Vol 24, Issue 02, 2020.
13. Rahimbayeva G. S., Tolibov D. S., Abduqaxxorov S. B. VERTEBROGEN ETIOLOGIYALI BEL-DUMG'AZA SOHALARIDA OG'IRIQLAR KUZATILGAN

BEMORLARDA KOMPLEKS DAVO QO'LANGANIDA SAMARADORLIGI
//Academic research in educational sciences. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. TMA
Conference. – С. 1085-1089.

14.Tolibov D. S. et al. Optimization of approaches to early diagnosis of
alzheimer's type dementia at the outpatient level. – 2022.

15.Tolibov D. S., Hadjaeva M. H. Analysis of clinical and neuroimaging parallels of
Alzheimer's disease–T //Materials of science conference. – 2012. – С. 185-186.

16.Tolibov D. S., Raximbaeva G. S. Aprobatsiya novogo diagnosticheskogo
kompleksa biomarkerov dlya differentsial'noy diagnostiki bolezni Algeymera
//Jurnal Meditsieskie novosti. – 2018. – №. 6. – С. 65-69.

17.Tolibov D., Rakhimbaeva G. Value of dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate
determination in the diagnosis of early forms of Alzheimer'/INS; s disease
//Journal of the Neurological Sciences. – 2013. – Т. 333. – С. e304.

18.Tolibov, D. S. "Neuropsychological features of Alzheimer's disease." Vestn.
TMA 2 (2013): 72-76.

19.Абдуллаева, Ч. А., and У. К. Камилова. "Взаимосвязь процессов
ремоделирования сердца с дисфункцией эндотелия у больных с
хронической сердечной недостаточностью." Кардиоваскулярная терапия и
профилактика 15.1 (2016): 16-19.

20.Абдуллаева, Ч. А., and У. К. Камилова. "Взаимосвязь процессов
ремоделирования сердца с дисфункцией эндотелия у больных с
хронической сердечной недостаточностью." Кардиоваскулярная терапия и
профилактика 15.1 (2016): 16-19.

21.Абдуллаева, Ч. А., and У. К. Камилова. "Взаимосвязь процессов
ремоделирования сердца с дисфункцией эндотелия у больных с
хронической сердечной недостаточностью." Кардиоваскулярная терапия и
профилактика 15.1 (2016): 16-19.

22.Абдуллаева, Ч. А., and У. К. Камилова. "Взаимосвязь процессов
ремоделирования сердца с дисфункцией эндотелия у больных с
хронической сердечной недостаточностью." Кардиоваскулярная терапия и
профилактика 15.1 (2016): 16-19.

23.Абдуллаева, Ч. А., and У. К. Камилова. "Взаимосвязь процессов
ремоделирования сердца с дисфункцией эндотелия у больных с
хронической сердечной недостаточностью." Кардиоваскулярная терапия и
профилактика 15.1 (2016): 16-19.

24.Абдуллаева, Ч. А., and У. К. Камилова. "Взаимосвязь процессов
ремоделирования сердца с дисфункцией эндотелия у больных с

хронической сердечной недостаточностью." Кардиоваскулярная терапия и профилактика 15.1 (2016): 16-19.

25.Рахимбаева Г. С., Толибов Д. С. Особенности нейровизуализации при диагностике болезни Альцгеймера //Вестник Казахского Национального медицинского университета. – 2015. – №. 3. – С. 86-88.

26.Рахматуллаев Х. Р., Джураев А. М., Халимов Р. Д. Хирургическое лечение болезни Пертеса у детей //В сборнике статей" Турнеровские чтения. – 2020. – Т. 54. – С. 304-307.

27.Саидвалиев Ф. С. и др. Расстройства сна при мигрени: обзор литературы и потенциальные патофизиологические механизмы //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. ТМА Conference. – С. 1163-1168.

28.Толибов Д. С. и др. Клинико-лабораторные особенности деменций альцгеймеровского типа //ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1.

29.Толибов Д. С., Рахимбаева Г. С. Особенности диагностики и терапии болезни Альцгеймера и сосудистой деменции. – 2019.

